

What are the equity in health challenges and implications of person-centred care for persons with advanced dementia? A systematic integrative review

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REVIEW TITLE AND BASIC DETAILS

Review title

What are the equity in health challenges and implications of person-centred care for persons with advanced dementia? A systematic integrative review

Original language title

What are the equity in health challenges and implications of person-centred care for persons with advanced dementia? A systematic integrative review

Review objectives

The main review question is:

What are the equity in health challenges and implications of person-centered care for persons with advanced dementia?

This main review questions is decomposed into the following research questions:

- Do gender, sociodemographic and socioeconomic characteristics influence person-centered care for persons with advanced dementia and how?
- Does vulnerability influence person-centered care for persons with advanced dementia and how?

Keywords

Advanced dementia, End-of-life care, Equity in health, Integrative review, Palliative care, Person-centred care, Systematic review

SEARCHING AND SCREENING

Searches

Searches will be conducted in the following databases: MEDLINE, Web of Science, Scopus, and CINAHL Complete and PsycINFO by EBSCO Discovery Service.

Preliminary searches were conducted in June 2024 and updated in September 2024. Final searches will be run in November/December 2024 and before the final analysis.

Studies in the following languages will be included: English, Portuguese, Spanish, French and German. There will be no restrictions on the year of publication.

Study design

Inclusion: Empirical studies using qualitative, quantitative, mixed-methods, intervention study approaches focused on equity will be included.

Exclusion: Non-empirical studies, reviews, case reports, case series, methodological papers, trials, editorials, commentaries, opinion pieces, grey literature will be excluded.

ELIGIBILITY CRITERIA

Condition or domain being studied

Equity in health is the absence of systematic disparities in health (or in the major social determinants of health) between groups with different levels of underlying social advantage/disadvantage, that is, wealth, power, or prestige (Braveman & Gruskin, 2003; Starfield, 2002). It is the absence of systematic and potentially remediable differences in one or more aspects of healthcare outcomes across socially, demographically, or geographically defined population groups. There is no basis for expecting a single characteristic or set of characteristics to be most influential in causing inequities in health. In fact, evidence suggests otherwise. Equity is an ethical principle. It also is consonant with and closely related to human rights principles.

Advanced dementia is a severe stage of dementia that causes significant cognitive and functional decline, memory loss, language impairment, and difficulty performing daily activities (Mitchel et al., 2009). Persons with advanced dementia (PwAD) are a highly vulnerable group, often exhibiting various categories of vulnerability, being neglected in their rights to high-quality care.

Evidence suggests the need to implement active strategies to improve person-centred care for PwAD. Access to high quality person-centred care for PwAD is often limited. In fact, care provision at the end-of-life for PwAD is often surrounded by uncertainty.

Population

Inclusion: Adults with advanced dementia, defined as severe stage of dementia that causes significant cognitive and functional decline, memory loss, language impairment, and difficulty performing daily activities.

Exclusion: Persons with other types of cognitive or mental disorders and/or cognitive impairment due to other diseases; persons with early and/or mild dementia.

Intervention(s) or exposure(s)

Inclusion: Empirical studies focused on equity in health challenges and implications of person-centered care for persons with advanced dementia using qualitative, quantitative, mixed-methods, trials or intervention study approaches focused on equity will be included.

Exclusion: Reviews, case reports, case series, methodological papers, editorials, commentaries, opinion pieces, grey literature will be excluded.

Comparator(s) or control(s)

Not applicable.

Context

Inclusion: Any context of healthcare provision for persons with advanced dementia will be included.

Exclusion: No context of healthcare provision will be excluded as long as it provides care to persons with advanced dementia.

OUTCOMES TO BE ANALYSED

Main outcomes

This review will reveal the equity in health challenges and implications of person-centered care for persons with advanced dementia. It will focus particularly (i) on whether and how gender, sociodemographic and socioeconomic characteristics might influence person-centered care for persons with advanced dementia and (ii) on whether and how vulnerability influences person-centered care for persons with advanced dementia.

Measures of effect

Not applicable.

Additional outcomes

Not applicable.

Measures of effect

Not applicable.

DATA COLLECTION PROCESS

Data extraction (selection and coding)

The articles retrieved from of the literature searches will be imported into EndNote and any duplicates will be removed. Data will be independently extracted by one reviewer (S.N.) in an iterative and dynamic process with the other two reviewers (P.H.M. and S.M.P.). Titles, headings, keywords, and abstracts will be screened for a multiple combination of MeSH, CINAHL headings, and free terms associated with “equity in health”, “advanced dementia”, “person-centred care”, and “vulnerability”. Any disagreements will be resolved by a consensus discussion among the three reviewing authors. The references of included studies as well of any seminal reviews about any of these topics will be screened for potential additional publications.

Data sheets will be used to extract data from the studies. Data will be extracted into a structured data form that will be purposely built for this study. This form will be based on and adapted from PICOS's (Methley et al., 2014; Eriksen and Frandsen, 2018): P = Population (persons with

advanced dementia, as per definition above), I = Intervention/exposure/phenomenon of Interest (equity in health challenges and implications of person-centered care for persons with advanced dementia), C = Context/Comparison (any context of care provision for persons with advanced dementia), O = Outcomes (whether and how gender, sociodemographic and socioeconomic characteristics might influence person-centered care for persons with advanced dementia; and whether and how vulnerability influences person-centered care for persons with advanced dementia), S = Study Design (empirical studies using qualitative, quantitative, mixed-methods, or intervention study approaches). Descriptive data will include authors, year of publication, country where the study was developed, year of the study, design, and number of participants in the study.

Risk of bias (quality) assessment

The methodological rigor of the included studies will be evaluated following the 9-item tool developed by Hawker et al. (2002). This tool has been widely used in the review literature since the nine questions are easily scored to assess the quality of the study and can even be transformed into a quantitative scale.

To minimize bias, two researchers (S.N. and P.H.M.) will screen the first 25% of retrieved articles independently. Articles will initially be screened by titles and abstract, followed by full-text reading of selected articles. Doubts will be discussed until reaching consensus with the third reviewer (S.M.P.).

Selected articles will be read full by two researchers independently (S.N. and P.H.M.) to identify eligible studies; any doubts will be discussed until reaching consensus among the three researchers.

PLANNED DATA SYNTHESIS

Strategy for data synthesis

A narrative synthesis will be undertaken and guided by Popay et al. (2006). Data synthesis will be performed by one researcher (S.N.) in an iterative and dynamic process with the other two reviewers (P.H.M. and S.M.P.). Main themes are defined a priori and aligned with the research questions as follows: (i) whether and how gender, sociodemographic and socioeconomic characteristics might influence person-centered care for persons with advanced dementia; and (ii) whether and how vulnerability influences person-centered care for persons with advanced dementia. All authors will work together to produce a comprehensive set of synthesized findings. The systematic literature review and narrative synthesis will be reported in accordance with the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Review and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) guidelines.

Analysis of subgroups or subsets

Not applicable.

REVIEW AFFILIATION, FUNDING AND PEER REVIEW

Review team members

- Professor Pablo Hernandez-Marrero, Universidade Católica Portuguesa, Católica Porto Business School, CEGE: Research Center in Management and Economics, Ethics and

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Review affiliation

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Funding source

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TIMELINE OF THE REVIEW

Review timeline

Start date: 01 October 2024. End date: 30 September 2025

Date of first submission to PROSPERO

30 September 2024

Date of registration in PROSPERO

11 October 2024

CURRENT REVIEW STAGE

Publication of review results

The intention is to publish the review once completed. The review will be published in English

Stage of the review at this submission

Review stage	Started	Completed
Pilot work		
Formal searching/study identification		
Screening search results against inclusion criteria		
Data extraction or receipt of IP		
Risk of bias/quality assessment		
Data synthesis		

Preliminary searches were conducted in the preparation of this protocol.

Review status

The review is currently planned or ongoing.

ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

Additional information

This review is being conducted as part of an international EU-funded project. Other collaborators might be added, depending on their contribution to the review.

PROSPERO version history

- Version 1.1 published on 11 Oct 2024
- Version 1.0 published on 11 Oct 2024

Review conflict of interest

None known

Country

Portugal

Other registration details

Not applicable.

Medical Subject Headings

Dementia; Humans; Patient-Centered Care; Socioeconomic Factors

Details of any existing review of the same topic by the same authors

Not applicable.

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